

Towards emission reduction in logistics procurement – experiences of building a multimodal emission-aware logistics marketplace

Jukka Kääriäinen, Markku Mikkola
VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland, Finland

Simo Salminen
Awake.AI Ltd., Finland

Summary: This paper outlines the collaborative development of the ADMIRAL emission-aware logistics marketplace, which incorporates sustainability into logistics sourcing by enabling emissions transparency, standardized calculation, and informed supplier selection. The paper presents the development pathway of the emission-aware logistics marketplace and discusses the main challenges encountered during its pathway. Furthermore, we present the structure and key features of the evolving marketplace as it is today. The insights gained provide useful information for researchers and for future digital platform developers seeking to promote more sustainable logistics solutions.

Keywords or phrases: marketplace, emissions, SCOPE 3, logistics, platform

Submission category: Working paper (WP)

Introduction

As requirements for SCOPE 3 emissions reporting and reduction become increasingly important, it is essential that emissions data from multimodal logistics chains can be estimated and calculated in a reliable and comparable manner. Companies seeking to reduce their overall logistics carbon footprint must be able to identify and evaluate low-emission logistics options already at the procurement stage, ensuring that sustainability considerations are integrated into purchasing decisions. Enhancing the visibility of emissions and low-emission alternatives during the logistics sourcing process empowers organizations to align their logistics choices with their environmental targets. One practical way to support this is the use of digital logistics marketplaces, which are now beginning to incorporate emissions calculation and reporting functionalities. These platforms enable logistics buyers to compare service providers not only by price and availability, but also by their environmental impact, thus supporting more informed and sustainable procurement decisions.

Digital logistics marketplaces can be seen as digital platform ecosystems designed to efficiently match logistics service providers with buyers, ensuring that specific supply meets corresponding demand as precisely as possible. In this paper, we examine the development of an emission-aware multimodal logistics marketplace and its ecosystem over a period of two and a half years in EU-funded project (ADMIRAL, 2025). The purpose of this paper is to present the lessons learned from the development of an emission-aware multimodal logistics marketplace and how it supports the procurement of sustainable logistics. At present, the first version of the marketplace has been implemented.

The paper is structured as follows. The paper begins by discussing the background of digital platforms and the types of functionalities that would best support emissions-aware purchasing. In the following section, we present the research design. The results section describes how the development of the marketplace platform ecosystem was carried out and presents the ADMIRAL marketplace ecosystem. In the discussion, we reflect on the challenges encountered and assess how well the established marketplace ecosystem meets the requirements for

emissions-aware purchasing. Finally, the conclusion summarises the findings and considers future research needs related to this topic.

Background

As the importance of reducing SCOPE 3 emissions continues to grow, it is equally important to be able to decrease the share of logistics emissions included within them. At present, transport accounts for a quarter of all greenhouse gas emissions across Europe, and this proportion is expected to increase as other sectors introduce more robust measures to reduce their emissions (Mikkola et al., 2025). Currently, there are efforts to systematize logistics emission calculation such as EU regulatory (CountEmissionsEU) as well as practical calculation frameworks that support the practical implementation of regulations like the GLEC (Global Logistics Emissions Council) Framework (Lewis et al, 2025; Royo et al., 2025).

However, achieving these objectives can be particularly challenging if providers and buyers of ecological logistics services are unable to find each other. Therefore, for sustainable logistics services to thrive commercially, it is essential that the offerings of environmentally responsible multimodal logistics service providers are easily available for purchasing decisions.

Digital marketplaces can be seen as digital platform ecosystems designed to efficiently match service providers with buyers, ensuring that specific supply meets corresponding demand as precisely as possible (Parker et al., 2016). In this sense, marketplaces act as traditional transaction platforms (Cusumano et al., 2020) that facilitate these matches and primarily focuses on the efficiency and volume of exchanges between participants (Parker et al., 2016). On the other hand, within the platform economy, innovation platforms (Cusumano et al., 2020) are referred to as platforms that allow third-party complementors to build additional services on top of the platform or integrate their existing information systems with it. The operation of these complementors, and the platform's ability to enable and regulate such engagement (e.g. by using boundary resources (Bianco et al., 2014)), is a significant feature of innovation platforms. Successfully combining these two approaches requires governance models that support both swift transactions and creative development, ensuring a balance between operational efficiency and the fostering of innovation (Cusumano et al., 2020; Mukhopadhyay and Bouwman, 2019). Digital logistics marketplaces are platforms especially targeted to support the selling and buying logistics services by providing the matchmaking of logistics offering and need (Bossong et al., 2025). These marketplaces can influence logistics business models, but the extent of this influence depends on how platforms are adopted and integrated by market stakeholders (Turienzo et al., 2024; Bajec et al., 2026). Companies face two main issues when implementing the marketplaces: identifying which transport needs and routes suit them, since requirements differ widely, and evaluating the business value of the marketplaces, as benefits like cost savings are hard to quantify given required investments and fees (Sylla, 2023). Regardless of the challenges, these marketplaces are now beginning to incorporate also emissions calculation and reporting functionalities (Mikkola et al., 2025), enabling logistics services buyers to compare service providers not only by price and availability, but also by their environmental impact, thus supporting more informed and sustainable logistics procurement decisions. When developing digital platform ecosystems, it is essential to consider a variety of aspects (Parker et al., 2016). These include defining the core interaction of the platform, identifying the key actors, clarifying the value creation logic, establishing governance structures, and understanding platform competition (Tura et al., 2018). However, reaching consensus on such definitions and developing practical solutions collaboratively can be complex. This complexity is highlighted e.g. by Valkokari et al. (2022), Hemilä et al. (2021) and Sylla (2023). Although digital platforms and platform ecosystems have been extensively studied, there remains significant room for longitudinal research on the development trajectories and dynamics of platforms (de Reuver et al., 2018; Pussinen et al.,

2023). Such studies could shed light on how platforms evolve over time and the factors that influence their ongoing transformation.

The Procurement Playbook Toward Zero Emissions Logistics Services (Smart Freight Centre, 2024) serves as a comprehensive resource for professionals striving to advance sustainability in logistics procurement. This guide advocates for the modernization of conventional procurement processes through a structured methodology aligned with recognised standards, making it applicable across all outsourced logistics services, irrespective of transport mode. The playbook details two primary strategies for achieving zero emissions in logistics: transactional procurement and transformational procurement. Transactional procurement capitalises on existing decarbonisation solutions within the supply chain, while transformational procurement calls for significant operational changes to facilitate the adoption of innovative decarbonisation measures. In this paper we reflect the transactional procurement strategy, as it is more relevant for the case context. The playbook recommends six key interventions to integrate sustainability into transactional procurement for logistics (Figure 1) (Smart Freight Centre, 2024), which can be linked to the generic transport purchasing models (Sylla, 2023; Monczka et al, 2009):

1. Sourcing Strategy: Align sustainable procurement with overall corporate sustainability goals to maximize the impact of carbon reduction initiatives.
2. Specification: Clearly define and standardize sustainable requirements, ensuring they align with RFI criteria and address supplier capability gaps.
3. RFI/RFP: Systematically incorporate sustainability requirements into RFI/RFP processes, linking supplier carbon performance to specific sustainability objectives.
4. Evaluation: Integrate sustainability criteria into supplier assessments to maximize organizational value, using simplified and efficient methods.
5. Contract: Update legal terms to include sustainability criteria, new technologies, and processes, addressing legal expectations and risk ownership.
6. Performance Management: Monitor supplier compliance with sustainability commitments, emphasizing visibility into carbon performance and other relevant metrics.

Figure 1 - Changes to integrate sustainability within logistics procurement (Smart Freight Centre, 2024).

Research design

The purpose of this paper is to present the lessons learned from the development of an emission-aware multimodal logistics marketplace and how it supports the procurement of sustainable logistics. The study adopts a qualitative longitudinal case study approach. Building on the

identified need for emission-aware logistics procurement and the role of digital marketplaces explained in previous section, this study examines:

- **RQ1:** How did an emission-aware logistics marketplace emerge and evolve, and which mechanisms supported its development?
- **RQ2:** How can an emission-aware logistics marketplace support procurement processes as defined in the SFC procurement playbook?

Case description

The Advanced Multimodal Marketplace for Low Emission and Energy Transportation (ADMIRAL) -project, is an EU-funded project with the objective of driving systemic change towards sustainability in the transport and logistics sector (ADMIRAL, 2025). The project started May 2023, and it will end April 2026. By facilitating better utilization of existing assets and infrastructure with the help of emission-aware multimodal logistics marketplace, the project seeks to reduce emissions and promote sustainable logistics procurement practices by matching emissions-aware buyers and sellers of logistics services. The aim of the project is to develop an emission-aware marketplace for multimodal logistics services. This initiative is being carried out in collaboration with research organizations, logistics service providers, and digital solutions developers (20 partners from 9 EU countries). The development of the ADMIRAL marketplace has been divided into two main areas: firstly, the advancement of the marketplace platform itself, and secondly, the creation of structures and tools that enable the functioning of the broader ecosystem. This includes both aspects: the transaction platform and the innovation platform (Mikkola et al., 2025). These parallel development streams ensure not only technical capabilities for facilitating logistics transactions but also foster an environment supporting to collaborative innovation and ecosystem growth.

Data collection

The empirical material consists of a rich set of qualitative data created throughout the project. The primary data source is a research diary compiled on a monthly basis, documenting key events, decisions, challenges, and interactions during the marketplace development process. This diary was maintained by three researchers from the EU project coordination organisation, enabling a comprehensive and consistent view of the project's progression. To strengthen the data, the research diary was complemented with multiple secondary data sources, including minutes from the project's management committee and consortium meetings, monthly work package meetings, developer forum discussions, and documentation available on the project's business and developer portals. Secondary data allowed cross-validation of observed events and emerging interpretations. Combining these sources enabled data triangulation and enhanced the transparency and understandability of the development process.

Data analysis

The data analysis followed a descriptive longitudinal logic. First, the monthly entries and data from complementary documents were synthesised into a chronological timeline capturing the evolution of the marketplace across three levels of platform ecosystem development: strategic, coordination, and production. These levels, adapted from prior literature (Valkokari et al., 2022; Kääriäinen et al., 2021) on platform ecosystem development, provided a structure for organising and interpreting the observed activities. The constructed timeline was reviewed by another researcher and by a project partner company who is responsible for implementing the marketplace. This was used to enhance the reliability of the interpretation.

The activities of the timeline were grouped into distinct phases in the evolution of the platform ecosystem. For example, early activities emphasised concept definition, stakeholder workshops, and the establishment of basic structures, which collectively formed the foundation

building -phase. Similarly, the later activities of the timeline highlighted increasing technical development, stakeholder activation, and demonstrations, eventually culminating in consolidation efforts. The grouping was reviewed by another researcher to enhance the reliability of the interpretation. Finally, the capabilities of the marketplace were preliminarily examined in relation to the six interventions of the Smart Freight Centre's procurement playbook, allowing a structured comparison between marketplace functionality and sustainable logistics procurement practices.

Results

ADMIRAL marketplace development lifecycle

The timeline was constructed from research data, following the levels of platform ecosystem development outlined in the research design section (Figure 3). The timeline presents the main activities and outcomes at each level: at the strategic level, the development of the ADMIRAL marketplace concept is shown; at the coordination level, the evolution of ecosystem tools/systems and the ecosystem itself are detailed; and at the production level, the development of the marketplace platform is described.

It is noteworthy that the development of the ADMIRAL marketplace did not start from scratch. The platform company had already established the Port marketplace for the sale of port services, which provided a substantial foundation for subsequent development efforts. However, the development of a multimodal emission-aware logistics marketplace requires a significantly broader approach. This needed the establishment of mechanisms essential for effective ecosystem coordination. Such mechanisms include various social boundary resources, for instance, a developer portal, discussion forums, and hackathons, all designed to support collaboration and foster innovation within the ecosystem.

To steer this development process, a strategic level was required, wherein the vision and concept for the marketplace were developed to guide the formation and evolution of both the marketplace and its supporting ecosystem. This strategic oversight ensured alignment between technical progress and collaborative ecosystem advancement.

Four main phases were identified as critical milestones in the development of the ADMIRAL marketplace (Figure 3). During these phases, various challenges were encountered, and solutions were found to overcome them, ensuring the project could progress despite the obstacles faced.

In May 2023, the project was launched, marketplace stakeholders were identified, the initial concept was defined, and the platform starting point was analysed. One of the most important things is the definition of the core interaction of the platform – what is the most important interaction the platform supports and who are needed for that interaction. A significant achievement was also the early adoption of the GLEC framework, laying the foundation for sustainable logistics development. Discussions with cargo owners and logistics partners began, and stakeholder workshops were conducted to build common understanding of the marketplace vision and concept.

In 2024, the focus was on technical development, including selecting portal and discussion tool technology and preparing documentation to better understand the intended functionality of the marketplace. A hackathon was organized to engage stakeholders and promote innovation related to the logistics emission management. Pilot planning and API integrations progressed, and the perspective of marketplace stakeholders (e.g. cargo owners, logistics service providers) through interviews was actively included in the marketplace design.

Figure 2 - Timeline of ADMIRAL marketplace development – strategic, coordination and production levels.

Figure 3 - ADMIRAL marketplace development path.

In 2025, marketplace demonstrations were held for ADMIRAL partners. An internal marketplace release and a clickable demo video were added to the website. The ecosystem of interested companies grew to over 30 registered partners. When writing this, the plan for 2026 is that the project is expected to reach the consolidation phase including e.g., the release of the second version of the marketplace API, further demonstrations, developer feedback gathering, and finalization of the concept. The marketplace ecosystem concept contains the description of vision and functionality, actors, business models and governance model.

The challenges in developing the marketplace ecosystem were primarily related to building a shared understanding and ensuring sufficient communication among the various actors. These aspects were essential to make the ecosystem attractive to all parties—sellers, buyers, as well as application developers and integrators.

The absence of a shared vision made it difficult to engage different stakeholders and establish a clear direction for the development work. This was addressed by organizing workshops and developing a vision (big picture & elevator pitch) to clarify the project’s target. It was also observed that the perspective of cargo owners was underrepresented. This was addressed through active involvement and feedback rounds (workshops), ensuring their views were incorporated into concept development.

Another challenge was that pilots and software companies struggled to understand the marketplace’s intended functionality and potential. The solution was to define concrete use cases and visualizations. Communication was initially fragmented, mainly via email and workshops, but this was solved by establishing a discussion forum for open and centralized interaction. Finally, the lack of understanding of integrations made it hard for SW development stakeholders to understand the technical implementation. Integration plans in developer portal (discussion threads for each pilot integration), marketplace demonstrations, pilot discussions and a clickable demo video were used to clarify these issues.

ADMIRAL marketplace

The first version of the ADMIRAL marketplace has been implemented (Figure 4, Figure 5). It targets to streamline the processes of selling, sourcing, fulfilling, and tracking low-emission, multimodal transport services—excluding air freight—as well as related hub operations. The platform provides visibility of emissions data across diverse multimodal logistics chains. By

connecting logistics providers from different transport sectors, the marketplace encourages a more seamless and effective utilization of resources within complex supply chains.

ADMIRAL Multimodal Marketplace

Figure 4 - ADMIRAL multimodal emission-aware logistics marketplace

Functioning as a collaborative environment, the marketplace gives logistics service providers the tools to showcase their service options, including both conventional and environmentally friendly choices. It also enables buyers who prioritize emissions data to launch tenders, select the most suitable logistics partners, manage orders, and access detailed reports on service completion and performance.

Beyond standard transactional features, the marketplace works as an innovation platform. It invites external developers and systems integrators to create and connect their own applications via technical interfaces, such as APIs. To further support this capability, the marketplace offers a dedicated developer portal and discussion forums (Figure 6). These resources foster collaboration, enable knowledge sharing, and make it easier for third-party developers and integrators to build innovative solutions on top of the platform.

During the project, proposals for the business models and the governance model of the platform ecosystem have been developed for the marketplace. Business models consider the benefits and costs for different actors operating within the marketplace. In turn, the governance model outlines the framework for how the marketplace operates, covering aspects such as ownership, decision-making processes, control (including access to the marketplace and ensuring the quality of contributions), and the boundary resources.

Regulatory frameworks—including CountEmissionsEU and GLEC—necessitate the estimation, calculation, and documentation of emissions across multimodal logistics operations. The marketplace is equipped to support the entire logistics journey, from order placement and fulfilment to final reporting, by enabling emissions estimation during the request-for-quotation stage, updating figures as the service progresses, and delivering precise emissions calculations once the logistics activity is complete. The marketplace also aggregates performance data and feedback from service providers, allowing for the identification of the most reliable providers and, thereby, increase trust. Additionally, it compiles summary

information for users regarding their own company’s procurements and the associated emissions, supporting companies in aligning their activities with their emissions reduction targets.

Figure 5 - ADMIRAL marketplace

Figure 6 - Business and developer portal

Next, a brief scenario is presented in which a logistics service buyer searches for suitable logistics and hub providers to meet their specific needs. The ADMIRAL marketplace (Figure 7) enables buyers—often freight forwarders—to build multimodal logistics chains by selecting from a range of seller services, such as road, rail, port services, and sea transport, each with detailed parameters like vehicle type and energy source. Buyers can compare estimated emissions for each segment using GLEC-compliant calculations, helping them make informed choices based on emissions data. The platform uses colour coding to clearly indicate emission levels: green for low, light green for reduced, and red for traditional, supporting buyers in choosing more sustainable transport options before launching a more detailed request for quotation (RFQ).

Figure 7 - ADMIRAL marketplace view with multimodal logistics and GLEC based emission calculations

Discussion

In this paper, we present the lessons learned from the development of an emission-aware multimodal logistics marketplace and how it supports the procurement of sustainable logistics. Beyond outlining the chronological development, the analysis revealed two underlying mechanisms that shaped the evolution of the marketplace:

1. **Vision alignment**, which was essential for coordinating heterogeneous set of stakeholders, understanding core interaction and establishing a shared direction for development.
2. **Engaging communication and collaboration**—including several boundary resources, such as the creation of a developer portal, facilitation of discussions, and hackathons/demonstrations—which enabled broader ecosystem participation and lowered barriers to entry.

The development of the emission-aware multimodal logistics marketplace highlighted the critical importance of establishing a shared vision of emission-aware multimodal logistics marketplace. Early in the project, the lack of a common understanding regarding the platform's purpose and core interaction posed challenges for collaboration. This aligns with prior research emphasizing that a clearly defined vision and identification of the platform's essential interaction are prerequisites for successful platform ecosystem development (Valkokari et al., 2022; Parker et al., 2016; Hemilä et al., 2021; Gawer and Cusumano, 2014). Through targeted workshops and iterative vision-building, stakeholders were able to progress towards a common understanding of the marketplace for all parties.

Later in the project, pilots and software companies had difficulty understanding the marketplace's intended functionality and potential in order to define integrations that would benefit them. Practical mechanisms played a pivotal role in facilitating co-creation and overcoming these communication barriers. The introduction of tools such as a developer portal, discussion forums, demonstrations, and hackathon, as well as the use of concrete visualizations and use cases, enabled more effective engagement of diverse stakeholders. These mechanisms not only supported technical integration (e.g. using APIs) but also fostered a collaborative environment where feedback and discussion were possible and new innovative usage scenarios could be ideated. Various participatory approaches—also referred to as boundary resources (Mukhopadhyay and Bouwman, 2019; Bianco et al., 2014)—in platform ecosystems play a crucial role in fostering shared understanding within the development community. These mechanisms not only facilitate collaboration and knowledge exchange but also support the emergence of new innovations by enabling diverse actors to contribute and co-create solutions.

The platform ecosystem development process has now resulted in the initial implementation of a multimodal emission-aware logistics marketplace. However, the marketplace is still initial version and not in business use. It should be noted that, accordingly, the analysis against the SFC procurement playbook remains very preliminary at this stage (Table 1). Further evaluation and refinement will be necessary as the marketplace and its processes continue to evolve before business use. This article also points to a promising avenue for future research, particularly by highlighting the need for more longitudinal studies on the emergence and development of platform ecosystems as stated also by de Reuver et al. (2018) and Pussinen et al. (2023). Such studies could shed light on how platforms evolve over time and the factors that influence their ongoing transformation. Also, Sylla (2023) acknowledges that marketplaces are not static and highlights the need for further research on how marketplaces and their use evolve over time.

In the following, we provide a preliminary examination of the marketplace in relation to the SFC procurement playbook (Table 1). With regards to sourcing strategy intervention, to maximize the impact of carbon reduction initiatives, the ADMIRAL marketplace aligns sustainable procurement with overall corporate sustainability goals. On the buyer side, the platform consolidates company-specific reports, including emissions data. These reports can

be used for both internal and external reporting, as well as for tracking and steering progress towards the emission reduction targets set by the company.

Regarding support for specification, the marketplace has well-defined information content and also specifies that emissions accounting must comply with the agreed emission calculation standards. In the initial phase, the focus is on GLEC-compliant calculation.

Sustainability requirements are systematically integrated into RFI/RFP processes. For buyers, the marketplace-generated RFQs include sustainability options. For sellers, emissions information is required in product and service listings.

To support evaluation, the marketplace enables buyers to consider the sustainability of the suppliers. For example, service alternatives' emissions are compared using a simple traffic-light style system. Emission information can be seen on TCE (Transport Chain Element) and hub (sea and land hubs) level.

Supporting contracting for both buyers and sellers, RFQs that include sustainability options form the basis for contracts between the parties.

With regards to performance management, the ADMIRAL marketplace monitors supplier compliance with sustainability commitments by collecting performance data, supplier ratings, and feedback. This emphasizes visibility into carbon performance and other relevant metrics.

Table 1 – Preliminary mapping of SFC playbook interventions and ADMIRAL marketplace functionality.

SFC procurement playbook interventions to transactional procurement process	ADMIRAL marketplace and solutions contribution
1. Sourcing Strategy: Align sustainable procurement with overall corporate sustainability goals to maximize the impact of carbon reduction initiatives.	Buyer side: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The marketplace will consolidate company-specific reports including emissions data, which can be utilized for both internal and external reporting, as well as for tracking and steering progress towards emission reduction targets set in the company.
2. Specification: Clearly define and standardize sustainable requirements, ensuring they align with RFI criteria and address supplier capability gaps.	Buyer and seller side: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Marketplace identifies/specifies how service listings are provided. Well-defined information content. Emissions accounting must comply with the agreed emission calculation standards. In the initial phase, the focus is on GLEC-compliant calculation.
3. RFI/RFP: Systematically incorporate sustainability requirements into RFI/RFP processes, linking supplier carbon performance to specific sustainability objectives.	Buyer side: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The marketplace-generated RFQs include the sustainability preferences. Seller side: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Emissions information is required in the product/service listings.
4. Evaluation: Integrate sustainability criteria into supplier assessments to maximize organizational value, using simplified and efficient methods.	Buyer side: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Simple traffic-light style comparison of service alternatives' emissions. Seeing estimated emissions in TCE and hub level.
5. Contract: Update legal terms to include sustainability criteria, new technologies, and	Buyer & seller side: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> RFQs including the sustainability options form the basis for the contract between buyer and seller.

processes, addressing legal expectations and risk ownership.	
6. Performance Management: Monitor supplier compliance with sustainability commitments, emphasizing visibility into carbon performance and other relevant metrics.	Buyer side: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Marketplace collects performance data and supplier ratings & feedback.

Conclusions

This study demonstrates how the ADMIRAL multimodal emission-aware logistics marketplace was developed in ADMIRAL project. The marketplace integrates sustainability into logistics procurement by supporting emissions visibility, standardized calculation, and supplier selection. Vision alignment and practical co-creation mechanisms, such as developer portals and stakeholder workshops, proved essential for building understanding, aligning diverse interests and fostering innovation. Since the marketplace has now reached its first version and is not yet in business use, ongoing ecosystem engagement and technical development remain critically important. The initial analysis indicates that the marketplace meets many of the SFC playbook requirements. However, a more comprehensive evaluation will be necessary once the marketplace has reached a higher level of maturity. Even though the marketplace is still in its early stages, the insights gained from this study offer meaningful guidance for future digital platform initiatives that aim to support sustainable logistics.

The limitation of this study is that, while the project has successfully developed the functional version of the marketplace, the marketplace is still under further development before it is ready for business use. Therefore, there is currently no evidence regarding its actual business capability in the logistics market. We propose a longitudinal study to track how the marketplace, its business models, governance model, and the surrounding ecosystem evolve over time. Such findings would be highly valuable from both research and practical perspectives.

Acknowledgments

This conference paper has been produced as part of the ADMIRAL project, which is co-funded by the European Union under grant agreement number 101104163 as part of the Horizon Europe programme (HORIZON-CL5-2022-D6-02-01).

References

ADMIRAL, 2025, ADMIRAL project pages. <https://www.admiral-project.eu/> . Retrieved 17.11.2025

Bajec, P., Zanne, M., Kääriäinen, J., Mikkola, M., Mulhern, E., Bajor, I. (2026) “Business Model (BM) Transformations in Business-to-Business (B2B) Digital Multimodal Logistics Platform Ecosystem: Insights from Prospective Marketplace Sellers and Buyers”, *Periodica Polytechnica Transportation Engineering*, 54(2), pp. 150–163. <https://doi.org/10.3311/PPtr.41651>

Bianco, V. D., Myllärniemi, V., Komssi, M., Raatikainen, M., 2014. The role of platform boundary resources in software ecosystems: A case study. *Proceedings - Working IEEE/IFIP Conference on Software Architecture 2014, WICSA 2014*, 11–20. <https://doi.org/10.1109/WICSA.2014.41>

- Bossong, P., Reinhardt, A., Elbert, R., 2025. Digital platforms in intermodal freight transport: An analysis of emerging business models and their future dynamics. *International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJPDLM-02-2024-0072>
- Cusumano, M. A., Yoffie, D. B., Gawer, A., 2020. The future of platforms. *MIT Sloan Management Review*, 61(3), Article 61304. Special Issue on Disruption.
- Gawer, A., Cusumano, M. A., 2014. Industry platforms and ecosystem innovation. *Journal of Product Innovation Management*, 31 (3), 417–433. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jpim.12105>
- Hemilä, J., Kääriäinen, J., Valkokari, K., 2021. Platform based Innovation Ecosystem Engagement Practices. In *Innovating our common future, Proceedings ISPIM Berlin 2021*, Lappeenranta University of Technology.
- Kääriäinen, J., Valkokari, K., Siira, E., Hemilä, J., Jurvansuu, M., 2021. Exploring the spaces and places for co-innovation. In *Innovating our common future, Proceedings ISPIM Berlin 2021*, Lappeenranta University of Technology.
- Lewis, A., Ehrler, V., Schön, A., 2025. Global Logistics Emissions Council Framework - For logistics Emissions Accounting and Reporting V3.2, March 2025, Retrieved from. https://smart-freight-centre-media.s3.amazonaws.com/documents/GLEC_FRAMEWORK_v3.2_21_10_25_1.pdf Accessed Nov 20th, 2025
- Mikkola, M., Kääriäinen, J., Hinkka, V., Pyykkö, H., Mulhern, E., Salminen, S., 2025. The Opportunities of Using a Logistics Service Marketplace to Decrease Emissions of Transport and Logistics Industry. In C. McNally, P. Carroll, B. Martinez-Pastor, B. Ghosh, M. Efthymiou, N. Valantasis-Kanellos (Eds.), *Transport Transitions: Advancing Sustainable and Inclusive Mobility: TRA conference 2024* (Vol. 4, pp. 318-323). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-95284-5_45
- Monczka, R. M., Handfield, R. B., Giunipero, L. C., Patterson, J. L., 2009. *Purchasing and supply chain management*. South-Western.
- Mukhopadhyay, S., Bouwman, W. A., 2019. Orchestration and governance in digital platform ecosystems: a literature review and trends. *Digital Policy, Regulation and Governance*, 21 (4), 329–351. <https://doi.org/10.1108/DPRG-11-2018-0067>
- Parker, G. G., Van Alstyne, M. W., Choudary, S. P., 2016. *Platform revolution: How networked markets are transforming the economy and how to make them work for you*. W. W. Norton & Company.
- Pussinen, P., Wallin, A., Hemilä, J., 2023. The hope of exponential growth: Systems mapping perspective on birth of platform business. *Digital Business*, 3 (2), Article 100060. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.digbus.2023.100060>
- de Reuver, Mark; Sørensen, Carsten; and Basole, Rahul C., 2018. The Digital Platform: A Research Agenda, *Journal of Information Technology*, 33 (2), Article 3. DOI: 10.1057/s41265-016-0033-3
- Royo, B., Zhang, Y., Lewis, A., Dehdari, P., 2025. CO2 emissions in urban freight transport: Developing and testing the EcoLogistics tool. *Case Studies on Transport Policy*, 20, 101415. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cstp.2025.101415>
- Smart Freight Centre & Implement Consulting Group, 2024. *The Procurement Playbook Toward Zero Emissions Logistics Services*. <https://smart-freight-centre->

media.s3.amazonaws.com/documents/es010324_SFC_Procurement_playbook_A4_v8i.pdf. Retrieved 17.11.2025

Sylla, P., 2023. Electronic procurement of transportation services: An evaluation concept for electronic transportation marketplaces. Springer Gabler Wiesbaden. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-40403-1>

Tura, N., Kutvonen, A., Ritala, P., 2018. Platform design framework: conceptualisation and application. *Technology Analysis and Strategic Management*, 30 (8), 881–894. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09537325.2017.1390220>

Turienzo, J., Blanco, A., Lampón, J. F., Muñoz-Dueñas, M. del P., 2024. Logistics business model evolution: Digital platforms and connected and autonomous vehicles as disruptors. *Review of Managerial Science*, 18, 2483–2506. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11846-023-00679-0>

Valkokari, K., Hemilä, J., Kääriäinen, J., 2022. Digital Transformation - Cocreating a Platform-Based Business Within an Innovation Ecosystem. *International Journal of Innovation Management*, 26 (3), Article 240016. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S1363919622400163>